

THE IMPORTANCE OF READING IN LEARNING ENGLISH AND SOME STRATEGIES TO HELP IMPROVE READING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

While reading is an essential tool for the development of language and the understanding of a culture, it also plays a vital role in developing social skills. Reading helps children understand what different situations are like by showing them through books. In this article, I will look at how to keep learners motivated to read online. To achieve this objective you need to do a couple of things. It develops their imagination and creativity by exposing them to new worlds and teaching them that anything is possible.

Introduction. Reading is the most important skill we learn. It helps us understand what is happening around us, and how to make sense of it. Good readers are able to access information that can help them in school and beyond. Reading is one of the best ways to develop your English writing skills. But, not all reading materials are written at an advanced level. As a result, many native and non-native speakers may find themselves struggling to understand the content of these materials.

First of all, you can strengthen your reading habits and the reading environment as a whole. Focus on those learners who need the most support with their reading, because those who are already reading with willingness need not much of your effort.

First of all, praise their achievements so far. Remind them that reading time of 10 minutes a day is achievable when they compare it to other daily activities. Make sure you agree with class and individual goals and encourage learners to do online quizzes about the e-books. The idea here is to strengthen the group efforts in reading with learners supporting each other through different activities. Finally encourage learners to motivate each other. If they feel they are reading because everyone is doing it makes a big difference. One more thing makes time to reward achievements. There is no substitute for personal affirmation from the teacher or classmates

Now to keep learners motivated to read online agree on some goals for the class and for the learner. These can include the number of books read the number of words

read the time spent reading. Suggest for example month and month by month goals for lower levels and term by term goals for higher levels. On the basis of that 10 minutes, a day is the recommended minimum you can calculate roughly how long it would take learners of a particular level to read an e-book of a certain length or to read an e-book of a certain word count.

You can also ask individual learners to suggest their own goals and to share them with you. At the end of the month or term ask them how they are doing. They could use a bar chart to show progress or just simply emojis thumbs up thumbs down in the comments stream. Learners can also do online quizzes. There is one great place to check in terms of extensive reading. It's the extensive reading foundation on their website reader. It also has a leaderboard to encourage competition and keep learners motivated.

Method. Now encouraging learners to motivate each other is a really powerful tool. Here is an idea for how to encourage learners to do it. First, put the class into small groups in different breakout rooms. In each room, there should be a mix of learners. Some already have a good reading habits and some don't. Ask learners to chat about three questions

1. What are you happy about when you are reading

If necessary give them this sentence to get started we're happy about our reading because ...

2. What's the most difficult thing?

Give learners this sentence to get started the most difficult thing for us. Again this might include how to choose a suitable ebook or

how to make time for reading. Pick up on examples from learners who have overcome these difficulties and

3. What would you say to other learners?

Ask your learners what they would say to a class that was just about to begin extensive reading online in English. You could even ask them to role-play these conversations within the security of the breakout rooms.

Learners can motivate each other to read different ebooks by sharing video reviews which they can film just on their phones. You can ask learners to answer the questions. These are the key question:

- what's the title of the book?
- who is the author?
- why did you love it?
- why did you love it?
- what's your favourite character?
- what's your favourite scene?
- what's your favourite part or sentence?

Ask them to speak for about 30 seconds to get their message across. You can then share these meele reviews with other learners during the online lesson. Another great activity for getting learners to motivate each other is to make film posters. Tell the class to imagine the last ebook they read as a film which is being shown online or in the cinema and then ask learners to answer the questions.

First what's the title of the film maybe it's different from the title of the book

you can also give examples from the real world when a book was different from a film that was made based on it.

The next question is who are the actors. These could be global superstar actors or even learners from the class. Ask your learners to make a poster using for example PowerPoint slide. If learners have the time they can create simple special effects with images animations text and sound so the film poster can also become an advert

Discussions. Now let's look at an idea for rewarding achievements. An online awards ceremony is a great way for celebrating reading and to keep learners motivated. Before the awards ceremony, learners can vote for the best ebook in a range of categories. For example, best cover best story best male or female character best image best ending etc. They can do this by using an online polling app or by messages on WhatsApp or other social media channels. If learners are confident enough ask them to read the nominations and the winners and give out the oars. Learners will find it really fun to interact with each other within the same video call. You could even follow the format of an Oscar-style award with fancy clothes playing some background music or sound effects from your phone.

Finally, take the opportunity to give your own awards to learners for example most books read most improved readers. Remember to recognize all learners who have tried hard.

Results. Here's a summary to keep your learners motivated. You need to first strengthen the habit and the reading environment as a whole praise learner, praise their achievements and remind them of the reading time of those 10 minutes a day. Make sure you agree with the class or and individual goals and do online quizzes. This strengthens the group effort in reading finally encourage learners to motivate each other if they feel everyone is reading it makes a big difference. The last thing makes time and remembers to reward achievements. Personal affirmation from the teacher and classmates is a really powerful tool That's all on this topic the ideas in this video are also available in a free downloadable guide to using ebook graded readers

Reading as a group with friends or family is a fun way to practice your English speaking skills. Talk about the book before starting it, so that everyone is on the same page. Make sure that everyone has an idea of what the book will be about. This will help increase engagement and lead to more interesting discussions during reading time! Use questions such as "What do we already know about there's no better time than now! Get someone you know to join you in reading in English every day. Reading is a great way to improve your English skills, and the best part is that there's no better time than now. Get someone you know to join you in reading in English every day.

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